

Path Integral Formulation of Free Propagator and Maximum Entropy

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The Feynman path integral approach to calculating a quantum propagator $K(x, x_1, t)$ such that $W(x, t) = \int dx_1 K(x, x_1, t) W(x_1, 0)$ involves a purely classical Lagrangian. The form $\exp(i \int L(x, dx/dt) dt)$ and integration over all possible classical paths between $x_1, 0$ and x, t taken as tiny dt slices. For the free propagator, this calculation may be simplified by taking the Fourier transform of $K(x, x_1, t)$ which introduces $\exp(ipx)$ into the problem. We argue that taking the Fourier transform is not simply a math procedure as p represents physical (classical) momentum. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ appears in this approach as associating physical momentum with a wavelength. Furthermore, it seems that backward forward motion is allowed in each dt slice because constant momentum is a classical solution and any positive or negative momentum may be used with the slice. Thus, "quantum mechanical" features appear already in what seems to be a classical calculation through $\exp(ipx)$.

In an earlier note, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$, (the wavefunction of a free particle) may itself be treated as a conditional probability and obtained by maximizing Shannon's entropy $W \ln W$ subject to the constraint xW i.e. allowing the particle to move back and forth even at time $t=0$. From $\exp(ipx)$, one may desire a Lorentz invariant wavefunction so px becomes $px - Et$. Then, one may construct the free particle propagator directly from: $K(x, x_1, t) = \int dk \exp(ik(x-x_1)) \exp(i k^2/2m t)$ which matches the Feynman approach. In both cases, one uses classical physics and the idea of maximization of entropy. In the second approach, one considers a specific constant momentum p when maximizing W . In the Feynman approach, all momenta are included for a free particle because given that one has particle move from $x_1, 0$ to x, t any initial (constant) momentum is possible.

Thus, we argue that the Feynman propagator for a free particle follows the same statistical approach as the maximization of a free particle conditional probability (i.e. wavefunction) subject to the constraint xW . This constraint, which seems to represent some forward backward motion directly, appears indirectly in the Feynman approach as $\exp(ipx)$ does not appear unless one uses a Fourier transform (which represents a physical wavelength).

Feynman Free Particle Propagator

Following (1), the Feynman approach to calculating the free particle propagator is given as:

$$\int_{x_1(0)}^{x(T)} \exp(-i \int_{(0,T)} L(dx/t) dt) Dx \quad ((1))$$

Here $L(dx/dt)$ is the classical Lagrangian for a free particle i.e. $m/2 dx/dt dx/dt$ and Dx suggests one successive time slice dt after another where $dx = x(t+e) - x(t)$.

At this point, one may ask why one considers $\exp(i \int L dt)$. We argue that this seems to follow from a maximization of Shannon's entropy using $K(x_1, 0, x, t)$ as a probability subject to the constraint $\int K L dt$. $K(x_1, 0, x, t)$ is ultimately multiplied by $W(x_1, 0)$ (within an integral) which is a conditional probability so it seems it is not unreasonable to treat K as a probability. It seems that $\int L dt$ represents a kind of weight for allowed trajectories. It is known that $\delta \int L dt = 0$ is used in classical physics to obtain classically allowable trajectories. It will be seen later that $\int L dt$ is of the form of a Gaussian in $(x-x_1)$ for little time slices which is linked, through a Fourier transform, to a Gaussian in p . Thus, there is a Gaussian or random momentum distribution for p in a little time interval. This seems to indicate a statistical result (i.e. maximum entropy) we argue and is similar to entropic dynamics (2).

It seems that desired form may be obtained (in a hand-wavy manner) from maximizing:

$-K \ln(K) + b \int K L dt$ ((1b)) where variations are over classically allowed trajectories within little intervals t to $t+e$, otherwise one would not use Dx . The result is:

K proportional to $\exp(i \int L dt)$ if one chooses $b=i$. One may require that K be of the form $\exp(iS)$ because ultimately $W(x, t)$ for a free particle should be linked to $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and the form $\exp(iGx)$ allows for this.

$L(dx/dt) dt$ for a free particle is approximated as:

$$e m/2 [x(t+e) - x(t)]^2 / (ee) \text{ where } dt=e. \quad ((2))$$

Thus, $\int Dx \exp\{-i e m/2 [x(t+e) - x(t)]^2 / (ee)\}$ has the appearance of string of convolutions where a single convolution appears as $f(x+t)f(x)$. Each time slice occurs at a successive time. Here, there is a product of Gaussian type factors (with an overall $i m/2$) each at a successive time.

In (1), it is suggested that one use Parseval's theorem for convolutions i.e. the Fourier transform of convolutions is the product of Fourier transforms of the functions. In this case, there is only one function $\exp\{-i e m/2 [x(t+e) - x(t)]^2 / (ee)\}$ a Gaussian in $x-x_1$. The Fourier transform of a Gaussian is also a Gaussian so one has:

$$K(p, T) = G(e)^{T/e} \text{ where } T \text{ is the total time interval and } e=dt. \quad ((3))$$

$$G(e) = \exp(-im e/2 pp) \quad ((4))$$

At this point, we wish to argue that the Fourier transform is more than a mathematical procedure. "p" represents actual classical momentum which is a physical attribute of a moving free particle. In fact, the different paths in each time slice dt are characterized by different velocities or momenta. Thus, we argue that obtaining ((4)) already shows quantum features in a strictly classical theory because one has the Fourier term $\exp(ipx)$ which suggests that classical

momentum is linked to a periodic function or a wavefunction, something that does not appear in classical physics.

It may be noted that with the Fourier transform in each dt interval, one has positive and negative momenta p which suggests forward-backward motion. By calculating a Fourier transform $G(e)$ within each dt interval, positive and negative momenta are allowed in each slice giving rise to the backward forward motion of quantum mechanics versus a single constant momentum in one direction from $x_1,0$ to x,t as in classical motion.

Finally, one may take the inverse Fourier transform to obtain the spatial representation as shown in (1);

$$K(x_1,0,x,T) \text{ proportional to } \exp[-im(x-x_1)(x-x_1) / 2T] \quad ((5))$$

At first, it may appear that the objective is only to obtain ((5)), but we argue that features of quantum mechanics are already present with the introduction of the Fourier transform which allows for forward backward motion and a momentum function $\exp(ipx)$. This suggests periodic motion with a specific wavelength which should be as physical as the classical momentum p.

Obtaining the Free Propagator Directly from a Wavefunction

It is possible to obtain $\exp(ipx)$, the free particle wavefunction or conditional probability, from maximization of entropy subject to the constraint xW (suggesting backwards forwards motion). From this wavefunction, we argue one may obtain the free particle propagator using ideas of Lorentz invariance.

Following (3), we argue that a free particle statistically should have the same probability to be at any x. In such a case, one has a positive real constant for $P(x)$. If the particle has a kind of internal motion which yields a constant momentum on average over a small length lambda or if the particle has equal probability to be at each x on average (i.e. there is forward and backward motion), then $P(x)=\text{constant}$ may not fully describe the problem. One may need a conditional probability $W(p,x)$ which may be related to $P(x)=\text{constant}$. Furthermore, p the momentum, describes a rate of probability flow. We suggest maximizing Shannon's entropy using $W(x)$ subject to the constraint xW (suggesting that there is backward forward motion with the particle being a certain x on average). Thus, we maximize:

$$-W \ln W + bW x \rightarrow W \text{ proportional to } \exp(bx) \quad ((6))$$

If we do not want ((6)) to grow or decline and want the change in conditional probability d/dx to be proportional to p, then $b=ip$ or $W=\exp(ipx)$.

Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ follows in a classical sort of manner by maximizing Shannon's entropy of W with the constraint xW . The question now becomes: How does the conditional probability for the free

particle change in time? If one wishes to have a Lorentz invariant, then $p_x \rightarrow p_x - Et$ or $\exp(ip_x - iEt)$. In such a case, one may immediately write the free particle propagator as:

$$K(x_1, 0, x, t) = \int dk \exp(-ikx_1) \exp(ikx) \exp(-\hbar k^2/2m t) \quad ((7))$$

In other words one uses $W(x, k)$ eigenfunctions with weights of $\exp(-ikx_1)$ in a projector type manner. This approach may be extended to other cases e.g. the oscillator propagator etc.

Thus, one does not necessarily need the Feynman path integral formalism or even the eigenfunction approach ((7)) to find the propagator. For example, it may be found as related to a Green's function as well.

The point we wish to make, however, is that in obtaining the free particle propagator in the two approaches used here, $\exp(ip_x)$ the free particle wavefunction appears.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Feynman path integral formalism of the free particle propagator allows for classical acceptable motion within tiny dt slices using $\exp(i \int L dt)$ as a weight. For a free particle, acceptable motion is constant momentum, but any momentum, positive or negative may be used in the dt slice as a Fourier transform is employed in the calculation. This transform is not just a mathematical procedure because in $\exp(ikx)$, $\hbar k$ represents physical, classical momentum. Thus, already in the Feynman seemingly classical approach $\exp(ip_x)$ is present suggesting a wavelength associated with p . We suggest that $\int L dt$ may be thought of as a "constant" as variations of zero lead to classically acceptable trajectories. In the Feynman approach, $\int L dt$ becomes a Gaussian in $(x - x_1)$ for the free particle corresponding to a Gaussian in p in p space. This, we argue, is a random statistical (or maximum entropy) solution for the momentum distribution.

In addition, we argue that $\exp(ip_x)$ may be obtained directly by considering the wavefunction $W(x)$ as a conditional probability and maximizing Shannon's entropy with the constraint xW suggesting a kind of forward backward motion although on average $P(x) = \text{constant}$. With $\exp(ip_x)$ obtained, we suggest using Lorentz invariance to generalize this to $\exp(ip_x - iEt)$. The free particle propagator may be obtained using $K(x_1, 0, x, t) = \int dk \exp(-ikx_1) \exp(ikx) \exp(-\hbar k^2/2m t)$ (i.e. without path integrals.).

References

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